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The Ease of Obtaining Credit Globally

Between 2013 and 2022 it decreased on average by 2.58% for the countries considered

The definition of "ease of getting credit" in the WIPO-World Intellectual Property Organization document concerns the evaluation of the ease with which individuals and businesses can obtain external financing. This includes variables such as access to bank credit, availability of credit lines and the degree of protection of creditors' rights. It is often measured through indicators such as the World Bank's Doing Business, which examines the procedures, times and costs associated with obtaining credit.

Source: World Intellectual Property Organization

Link: https://www.wipo.int/edocs/pubdocs/en/wipo_pub_gii_2016-annex1.pdf

The ease of obtaining credit globally in 2022. The ease of obtaining credit globally in 2021, measured through scores assigned to various countries, reveals notable disparities across the world's economies. Countries such as Azerbaijan, Brunei Darussalam and New Zealand, which reach the maximum score of 100, represent excellent examples of facilitated access to credit. This indicates well-structured financial systems, favorable policies and a business environment that encourages lending and investment. These countries demonstrate strong protection of creditor rights and a robust financial infrastructure, which together create an ideal environment for access to credit for both individuals and businesses. These conditions are key to stimulating economic growth, innovation and sustainable development. Australia, Jordan, Kenya, Rwanda, the United States and Zambia, with a score of 95, follow closely behind, also demonstrating highly facilitated access to credit. This diverse group of countries highlights that regardless of the level of economic development or geographic region, effective credit policies can be successfully implemented. The adoption of laws and regulations that protect the rights of creditors, the presence of transparent and accessible credit information, and healthy competition in the banking sector are among the key factors contributing to these high scores. Colombia, Mexico, Malawi and Tajikistan, with a score of 90, reflect good access to credit, but with room for improvement. These countries are working to strengthen their financial infrastructure and improve the regulatory environment to further facilitate access to finance. The presence of effective credit bureaus, the availability of credit information, and an effective judicial system to resolve loan-related disputes are crucial to maintaining and improving these scores. Canada, Costa Rica, Georgia, Guatemala, Jamaica, Kyrgyzstan, Latvia, Montenegro, Nigeria, with a score of 85, show that although access to credit is relatively good, there are still challenges to address. The need to improve the quality of credit information, reduce bureaucracy and increase competition between lenders are among the measures that could further improve the accessibility of credit in these countries. Honduras, India, Kazakhstan, Cambodia, North Macedonia, Mongolia, Panama, Romania, the Russian Federation, El

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Salvador and Vietnam, with a score of 80, reveal a moderate credit access situation. These countries have made significant progress, but still face obstacles such as a lack of transparency in credit information, weak financial institutions, and regulatory complexities that can make it difficult to access loans, especially for small and medium-sized businesses. The United Kingdom, Hong Kong SAR, China, Hungary, Malaysia, Nepal, Peru, Poland, Singapore, Turkey and Ukraine, with a score of 75, indicate that access to credit is relatively easy, but there are significant barriers that prevent further improvement. The need for more inclusive policies, reducing barriers to entry into the credit market and implementing innovative financial technologies are among the areas that require attention to improve credit accessibility. Albania, United Arab Emirates, Armenia, Ivory Coast, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Estonia, Indonesia, Ireland, Israel, Lithuania, Moldova, Niger, Slovakia, Togo and Thailand, with a score of 70, show access to credit decent but not optimal. In these countries, implementing better risk management practices, expanding credit services and improving financial education could help make credit more accessible. Belgium, Bulgaria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Switzerland, Egypt, Republic of Korea, Mauritius, Senegal, Serbia, Trinidad and Tobago, Tanzania, Uzbekistan and Zimbabwe, with a score of 65, reflect access to credit which, although present, is hindered by various factors. Improving the transparency of credit information, developing robust financial institutions and reducing the costs associated with obtaining credit are strategies that could improve the situation in these countries. Botswana, China, Cameroon, Cyprus, Spain, Finland, Ghana, Laos, Namibia, Saudi Arabia, Sweden, Uganda, Uruguay and South Africa, with a score of 60, highlight the need for significant reforms to improve access to credit. These countries face challenges related to complex bureaucracy, restrictive financial regulation and a lack of competition in the banking sector. Austria, Bahrain, Chile, Iceland, Japan and Norway, with a score of 55, indicate that, despite developed economies, access to credit is limited by stringent regulations and complex bureaucratic systems. Introducing more flexible policies and encouraging innovations in the financial sector could facilitate access to finance. Argentina, Belarus, Brazil, France, Croatia, Iran, Tunisia, with a score of 50, show that the barriers to accessing credit are significant. The need for structural reforms, improved credit information and increased financial transparency are essential to make credit more accessible. Bangladesh, Dominican Republic, Ecuador, Greece, Italy, Kuwait, Morocco, the Netherlands, Pakistan, Portugal, Qatar and Slovenia, with a score of 45, reflect a credit access situation that can be improved through regulatory and institutional reforms. The introduction of better risk management practices and the expansion of financial services can help facilitate access to loans. Lebanon, Sri Lanka, Madagascar, the Philippines and Paraguay, with a score of 40, indicate significant challenges in accessing credit, due to economic instability, restrictive regulations and weaknesses in financial infrastructure. The need to stabilize economies and reform the financial sector is crucial to improving access to credit. Bolivia, Cape Verde and Malta, with a score of 35, together with Oman, Benin, Burkina Faso and Guinea, with scores between 30 and 25, highlight serious difficulties in accessing credit. These countries face significant structural challenges that require policy and regulatory interventions to make credit more accessible. Mozambique, with a score of 25, and Ethiopia, with 15, represent extreme cases where access to credit is severely limited. The need to build financial infrastructure and improve economic stability is crucial to improving access to credit in these countries. Finally, Algeria, Myanmar and Angola, with scores between 10 and 5, and Yemen, with zero, highlight critical situations where access to credit is almost non-existent. In these countries, political and economic instability, coupled with weak financial systems, create insurmountable barriers to accessing finance. The need for deep reforms and international support are essential to improve these conditions.

The ease of obtaining credit globally between 2013 and 2022. The landscape of ease of obtaining credit globally has seen significant changes from 2013 to 2021, with some nations making

extraordinary progress and others experiencing notable regressions. Among the countries that showed the most evident improvement, we find Azerbaijan, which saw an increase in the ease of obtaining credit from 68.8 to 100 points, with an absolute variation of 31.20 points and a growth percentage of 45,35%. This progression could be attributed to structural economic reforms and greater institutional support in the financial sector. Brunei Darussalam is another notable example, with an impressive increase from 43.8 to 100 points, highlighting an absolute change of 56.20 points and a percentage growth of 128.31%. This dramatic improvement likely indicates the implementation of favorable financial policies and expanded access to banking and credit services. In contrast, countries such as New Zealand and Australia, already at a very high level in 2013 with 93.8 points, showed only marginal changes. New Zealand reached the maximum of 100 points with an absolute change of 6.20 points, while Australia only saw an increase of 1.20 points to 95 in 2021. These minimal changes suggest that despite their credit system was already advanced, there was only a slight refinement rather than substantial transformations. Jordan's case is particularly notable, with a significant jump from 25 to 95 points. With an absolute change of 70 points and a percentage growth of 280%, Jordan has demonstrated a notable effort to improve access to credit, likely through aggressive financial reforms and institutional enhancements to promote financial inclusion. In Kenya, the ease of obtaining credit index increased from 87.5 to 95, showing an absolute change of 7.5 points and a growth percentage of 8.57%. Although this increase is smaller in absolute terms than in other countries, it reflects continued improvement in an already quite advanced credit system. In Latin America, Colombia and Mexico made notable progress, with Colombia seeing an increase from 62.5 to 90 points (a change of 27.5 points and a 44% increase) and Mexico going from 75 to 90 points (with a variation of 15 points and a growth of 20%). These increases indicate significant efforts to improve access to credit and support economic development through more favorable credit policies. In contrast, some nations have seen a decrease in the ease of obtaining credit. The UK, for example, saw a significant drop from 100 to 75 points, with an absolute change of -25 points and a percentage decrease of 25%. This decline may reflect economic and political uncertainties related to Brexit, which have negatively impacted confidence in the financial system. Hong Kong SAR, China, experienced a decrease from 93.8 to 75 points, a change of -18.8 points and a percentage reduction of 20.04%. Singapore also recorded a decline from 87.5 to 75 points, reflecting a reduction of 12.5 points and a degrowth of 14.29%. This data may indicate that, despite the advanced economies of these regions, there have been external and internal factors that have negatively affected access to credit. In Europe, countries such as Germany, Denmark and Ireland have all seen significant decreases. Germany and Denmark fell from 81.3 to 70 points, with a variation of -11.3 points and a percentage reduction of 13.90%. Ireland saw a more drastic decline, dropping from 87.5 to 70 points, a change of -17.5 points and a percentage reduction of 20%. These trends may be linked to broader economic factors and austerity policies that have affected the credit sector. Asia saw contrasting situations, with countries such as Japan recording a decline from 81.3 to 55 points (a reduction of 26.3 points and a percentage decrease of 32.35%), while others such as Tajikistan saw an incredible increase from 12.5 to 90 points (a change of 77.5 points and a growth of 620%). This suggests a large disparity in credit policies and economic reforms across Asian countries. Africa has shown both improvements and regressions. Countries like Madagascar saw growth from 12.5 to 40 points, a change of 27.5 points and a growth of 220%. However, other nations such as Angola saw a drastic drop from 43.8 to 5 points, reflecting a decrease of 38.8 points and a percentage reduction of 88.58%. In summary, the data indicates a varied panorama of the ease of obtaining credit at a global level, with significant improvements in some regions and worrying regressions in others. Positive changes are often linked to economic reforms and more favorable credit policies, while declines can be attributed to economic instabilities, restrictive policies or local and global economic crises. This

highlights the importance of economic policies and institutional reforms in determining access to credit and, consequently, in supporting economic development and inclusive growth.

Conclusions. The value of the ease of obtaining credit decreased between 2013 and 2022 by an average of -2.58%, going from 64.6 to 63. Among the countries that have had the greatest growth in terms of ease of obtain credit there are Tajikistan with a value equal to +620.00%, Jordan with +280.00%, Madagascar with +220.00%, Brunei Darussalam with +128.31%, and Malawi with +105,48%. Among the countries that have seen a significant decrease in the ease of obtaining credit are Luxembourg with -52.08%, Ethiopia with -70%, Algeria with -77.17%, Angola with -88, 58%, and Yemen with -100.00%. If we look at the 2022 data we can see that Anglo-Saxon countries have the highest levels of ease of obtaining credit among Western countries with New Zealand with a value of 100, Australia and the United States with 95, Canada with 85 and the United Kingdom with 75.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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References

Leogrande, A. (2024). Companies with at least 10 Employees Selling Online across the Italian Regions. Available at SSRN 4785815.

Leogrande, A. (2024). Regular Internet Users Across the Italian Regions. *Available at SSRN 4782193*.

Leogrande, A. (2024). Cultural and Creative Employment Across Italian Regions. *Available at SSRN*.

Leogrande, A. (2024). Knowledge Workers across the Italian Regions. *Available at SSRN 4772381*.

Leogrande, A. (2024). The Propensity for Patenting in the Italian Regions. *Available at SSRN 4771132*.

Leogrande, A. (2024). The Innovation of the Production System in the Italian Regions. *Available at SSRN 4771131*.

Resta, E., Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Anobile, F., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The Impact of Patent Applications on Technological Innovation in European Countries. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 28(3,), 1-15.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The Determinants of Innovation in European Countries in the period 2010-2019. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(8), 91-126.

Costantiello, A., Leogrande, A., & Laureti, L. (2021). The corporate innovation in Europe. Available at SSRN 3964043.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The innovation-friendly environment in europe. Available at SSRN 3933553.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2020). The finance-innovation nexus in Europe. *IJSET-International Journal of Innovative Science, Engineering & Technology*, 7(12).

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2021). The Impact of Venture Capital Expenditures on Innovation in Europe. Available at SSRN 3930697.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., De Cristoforo, G., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The Innovation-Sales Growth Nexus in Europe. Available at SSRN 3933407.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The innovation-employment nexus in Europe. Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A.(2020). The innovation-employment nexus in Europe. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(11), 166-187.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., Leogrande, A., & Matarrese, M. (2021). The Innovation Linkages in Europe. Available at SSRN 3983218.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). The Employment in Innovative Enterprises in Europe. Available at SSRN 4010098.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Matarrese, M. (2022). Innovative SMEs Collaborating with Others in Europe. Available at SSRN 4103840.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Marketing and Organizational Innovations in Europe. Available at SSRN 4186167.

Angelo, L., Laureti, L., & Alberto, C. (2022). The Innovation Index in Europe. Available at SSRN 4091597.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2022). The Impact of New Doctorate Graduates on Innovation Systems in Europe. Available at SSRN 4209643.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2022). The Role of Non-R&D Expenditures in Promoting Innovation in Europe. Available at SSRN 4215981.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2022). The opportunity driven entrepreneurship in the context of innovation systems in Europe in the period 2010-2019. Available at SSRN 4229027.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2022). The impact of patent applications on technological innovation in European countries. Available at SSRN 4275264.

Resta, E., Costantiello, A., Anobile, F., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The Impact of New Doctorate Graduates on Innovation Systems in Europe. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 28(3), 1-22.

Resta, E., Costantiello, A., Anobile, F., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The Opportunity Driven Entrepreneurship in the Context of Innovation Systems in Europe in the Period 2010-2019. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP*, 28(3,), 1-13.